

SiC COATING THROUGH CHEMICAL VAPOR DEPOSITION AND REACTION SINTERING ON CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the SiC coating is obtained from both the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process and the pressureless reaction sintering technique. In the CVD process, tetramethylsilane (TMS) is adopted as the reactant, and hot wall reactor is utilized for the SiC deposition. In the pressureless reaction sintering process, difluorosilylene is used as the reactant for Si deposition, the C/C composite with Si coating is then subjected to a pressureless sintering process for forming SiC layer at 1800⁰C. X-ray diffractometer is employed to examine the structure of the coating layer, and it is observed that the SiC layer obtained from reaction sintering shows a better crystalline structure than that obtained from CVD process. The morphology of SiC layers obtained from both processes are examined by SEM; the results show that SiC can be found not only on the specimen surface but also within the interior of specimen. EDXS results depict the existence of oxygen, a further investigation in this regard by ESCA is performed and the formation of silicon oxide within the deposition layer is detected.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced carbon matrix composites (C/C) show a very specialized group of materials for its unique characteristics at high temperature environment. The superior specific strength and low creep resistance can be maintained in high temperature application due to strong covalent bonding and highly anisotropic graphite structure[1]. Therefore, C/C composites have been adopted in manifold applications such as racing car brake discs, rocket nozzle exit cone, turbine wheel, leading edges and nose-caps of the space shuttle at al.[2,3]. However, some of the applications involve extended exposure of the C/C composites in oxidizing environment. Carbon reacts with oxygen very rapidly, as a result, the applications of C/C composites will be restricted because it gasify significantly at the temperature above 500⁰C[4].

On the investigation of protection of C/C composite from oxidation, several studies are being considered. It includes the additive of inhibitors within the matrix to slow down the oxidation rate and the construction of an antioxidation barrier layer onto the surface of C/C composites to prevent the oxygen from reaching the carbon substrate [1,4,5]. For the antioxidation coating on C/C composites, a number of materials involving B₂O₃, P₂O₅, SiO₂, SiC, ZrC, and ZrB₂ have been mentioned[1]. Among the coating materials mentioned, silicon carbide shows the best chemical and thermal expansion compatibility with the carbon substrate and has the lowest oxidation rates. The thermal expansion coefficients for the C/C composites are $-1.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ and $4.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ (room temperature to 600⁰C) in the direction parallel and perpendicular to the fiber, respectively, whereas the SiC is $3.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ (room temperature to 1000⁰C)[4].

In this study, the chemical vapor deposition technique is used to deposit SiC onto the C/C composites for forming an antioxidation coating layer. Two deposition temperatures are used to

examine the influence of processing temperature on the performance of coated layer for oxidation protection. On the other hand, the silicon layer can be obtained from the pyrolysis of difluorosilylene at a relatively lower temperature; the deposited silicon coating layer is then subjected to a high temperature at 1800°C for converting Si to SiC through a reaction sintering process. The morphologies of the deposited SiC and converted SiC are examined. EDXS and X-ray are also employed to study the composition elements and crystalline structure of the SiC layer.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The 2-D plain weave carbon fabrics are used as reinforcement and phenolic resin is adopted as binder and matrix precursor. The carbon fabrics are impregnated with phenolic resin using a wet dipping technique and the compression molding is applied under a pressure of 17.25 MPa at 150°C. The resulting 8 layers polymer composites are post-cured in a circular air oven at 150°C for 36 hours. After post-cured process, the composites are cut into 50mm x 10 mm x 1 mm test specimens using a diamond-tip saw under water cooling. the carbonization process is carried out under argon atmosphere in the Linberg high temperature tube furnace to 1200°C with a heating rate of 30°C/hr.

PARTIAL DENSIFICATION OF C/C COMPOSITES

The densification of carbonized C/C composites are performed in a horizontal tube furnace by the isothermal chemical vapor infiltration (ICVI) method. Methane is used as a precursor of the deposited carbon and argon is used as a carrier gas. The methane volume fraction is 75%. After the furnace temperature reached the processing temperature for 30 minutes. The gas mixture is channelled into the reactor with a flow rate of 100cc/min.

Si DEPOSITION ON C/C COMPOSITES

Si layer obtained from the thermal decomposition of SiF₂ are well documented[6]. The decomposition process is performed in a hot wall LPCVD reactor which is connected to a SiF₂ generator. Once the deposition reactor and the SiF₂ generation chamber are heated to the desired temperature and the reactor is evacuated to the pressure of 10⁻³ Pa, the SiF₄ gas at room temperature is introduced into the SiF₂ generation chamber. The deposition of Si occurs at 400°C under a pressure of 150 Pa for 5 hours.

SiC DEPOSITION ON C/C COMPOSITES

SiC layer is derived from the thermal decomposition of Si(CH₃)₄ in this study. The decomposition process is performed in a hot wall LPCVD reactor at 1050°C under a pressure of 10 Pa for 1.5 hours.

REACTION SINTERING FOR FORMING SiC

Both the Si and the SiC coated specimens are subjected to a pressureless reaction sintering process which is carried at 1800°C on a graphite furnace produced by Thermal Technology Inc. Model 100-3060-FP20 under argon atmosphere at a constant flow rate of 100 cc/min with a heating rate of 3°C/min.

EXAMINATION OF MICROSTRUCTURE

SEM examination is performed in a JOEL 840A microscope with energy dispersive X-ray analytical (EDXS) capability. X-ray diffraction (XRD) is utilized to investigate the crystalline

structure. The XRD patterns are obtained with Cu-K α radiation using a Siemens D5000 diffractometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures (1a) and (1b) represent the XRD patterns of SiC coating derived from TMS pyrolysis process and conversion method, respectively. The transformation of silicon coating to silicon carbide can be confirmed from pattern (1b). However, the peaks(2 θ) show in (1a) and (1b) are not very sharp; a broader peak at 26.1, which represents the carbon polycrystalline structure, is observed, this is due to the curve contour surface of the C/C composites. The broader peak can be improved, as shown in Figure (1c), when a plain graphite surface is used for substrate.

XRD is also used to examine the crystalline structure of Si on C/C composite surface, no peak is observed. In order to get an insight into detail, ESCA analysis is used, and a peak characteristic for silicon at 99.3 eV, as shown in Figure 2a, is detected. The results also show that silicon oxide forms throughout the deposited layer although a concentration gradient of oxygen is observed(Figure 2b). Thus, it is concluded that the deposited silicon reacts with oxygen in air during handling.

Figure 3 depicts a global overview of the Si coating within and on the surface of the C/C composites. The white segments represent the Si deposition, it is observed that the deposited Si scattered through the composite; it distributes not only on the surface but also in the deep interior of the composite. Figure 4 shows the Si deposition on a crack surface within the composite; no obvious deposition gradient within crack is found. The scattered and uniform deposition of the Si within composite implies that the composite can be coated with a SiC layer when the conversion process for forming SiC is performed.

Figure 5 shows the deposition morphologies of Si in a fracture surface. A uniform coated layer around carbon fiber is observed. On the surface of the coated layer, fragment-like depositions are also detected. The EDX spectrum shows that the compositions of fragment-like materials contain silicon with a little amount of carbon which results from the deflection of the underlying carbon fiber.

Figures 6 and 7 represent the deposited layer in C/C composite which is subjected to 1800°C reaction sintering. The layer shown in Figure 6 is a carbon coating which is obtained from the partial densification process. The pore is prematurely closed in the process; therefore, no further infiltration of the Si precursor into the pore is achieved during the afterward Si deposition process; thus the carbon layer can't convert to SiC due to the lack of Si even if a high temperature conversion process is applied. Figure 7 shows the converted SiC layer on the composite surface. Figure 8 depicts the EDX spectrum of the converted layer, the peak at 0.523 keV is the oxygen peak; the peaks at 0.928 keV and 1.523 keV, which show the composition of the specimen holder, is detected.

Figure 9 depicts the morphology of the SiC deposition layer, a relatively uniform coating is observed; moreover, no obvious debonding between fiber and deposited layer is detected. EDX spectrum of the coating layer is shown in Figure 10. A peak at 0.523 keV is still present, which implies that the reaction of the SiC (free silicon) with oxygen occurs.

CONCLUSIONS

SiC coatings obtained from CVD and reaction sintering are examined. The results show that the bonding between deposition layer and reinforcements is quite well although a heat treatment at 1800°C is performed. EDXS results show that oxygen is detected in specimen obtained from

both processes. ESCA result depicts that oxygen is observed not only on the surface but also within the deposition layer. Although a preliminary study on the performance of the antioxidation behavior of the coated layers obtained from two difference processes is performed, a further investigation is still required.

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REFERENCES

1. J.R. Strife and J. E. Sheehan, "Ceramic Coating for Carbon-Carbon Composites", Ceramic Bulletin, Vol. 67, No.2, (1988).
2. G. Savage, Carbon-Carbon Composites, Chapman & Hall, New York, (1992).
3. A. J. Klein, Carbon-Carbon Composites, Advanced Materials & Processes inc. Metal Progress, 11/86, (1986).
4. F.J. Buchanan and J.A. Little, The growth and Morphology of Chemically Vapour Deposited Silicon Carbide Coating on Carbon-Carbon Composites, Surface and Coating Technology, Vol.46, (1991).
5. T. Cordero, P.A. Throver, and L.R. Radovic, On the Oxidation Resistance of Carbon-Carbon Composites Obtained by Chemical Vapor Infiltration of Different VCarbon Cloths, Carbon, Vol.30, No. 3, (1992).
6. C.C. Chen, T.L. Yu, C.Y. Lee, C.S. Liu, and H.T. Chiu, Difluorosilylene as a Precursor for the Chemical Vapor Deposition of Titanium Silicide, J. Mater. Chem., 2(9), (1992).

Figure 1. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the (a) SiC coating, (b) SiC layer converted from Si at 1800°C, and (c) SiC converted from Si coating on a plain graphite substrate .

Figure 2. (a) XPS spectrum of silicon and silicon oxide (Si_{2p} peak) in silicon coating. (b) Depth profile of the Si-coated layer on C/C composites.

Figure 3. A global overview of the Si coating within and on the surface of the C/C composites.

Figure 4. Si deposition on a crack surface within the composite.

Figure 5. Deposition morphology of Si in a fracture surface

Figure 6. Carbon coating in a pore of the C/C composite which is subjected to the heat treatment at 1800°C.

Figure 7. Converted SiC layer after heat treatment at 1800°C.

Figure 8. EDX spectrum of the converted SiC layer.

Figure 9. Mophology of the deposited SiC layer.

Figure 10. EDX spectrum of the deposited SiC layer